

Role of pada dhara therapy as a bahya snehan and upnaha swedan effect in various types of peripheral neuritis

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Abstract

Dhara is a part of *Keraliya Panchkarma* which means pouring liquid medium in a thin, continuous, stream over the body or affected area, when it is done all over the feet it is known as *PadaDhara*. It comes under *Parisheka Swedana*. *Dhara* means pouring liquid medium in a thin, continuous, stream over the body or affected area. In this, medicated oils are poured over the body in streams for a fixed duration of time as is done in any type of *Dhara*. It has been truly stated that *Dhara* is good for almost all diseases. The word *Pada* refers to feet and *Dhara* means to pour, mainly medicated oil. It is a very unique procedure mentioned as '*Snehayukta Swedana*' due to the fact that it comprises both *Snehana* (therapeutic oleation) and *Swedana* (sudation therapy)¹.

The *Taila* (oil) used for this procedure does the *Snehana* and due to the *Agni Samyoga* in this procedure it has the resulting *Swedana* effect. *Vata dosha* play main role in this Diseases. In this case study, the management should be in such a way that it should bridle the aggravated *vata dosha* and *dhatukshaya*. *PadaDhara* and *Upanaha sweda* is considered as the best *vata shamka*. *Pada Dhara* is advised in painful conditions caused mainly by *Vata Dosha*, usually for degenerative diseases, *Pada Chimchimayan* Peripheral Numbness, Tingling sensations at feet along with painful pricking sensations At the end of the procedure perspiration is noticed and an increased range of motion can be observed *Pada Dhara* have both Properties *snehna* and *swedna* effect. *Bahya snehana* and *swedna* are two important treatment Modalities to action of Aggravated *vata dosha*. *Pada Dhara* helps to tone muscles, provides lubrication and improves the working mobility of the joint. and soothing effect over peripheral nerves²

Keywords: Pada Dhara; Sthanik Swedana; Parisheka; Peripheral Neuritis

1. Introduction

Acharya Charaka has classified *Trividha Aushadhi* as *Anta-Parimarjana* (internal therapies), *Bahi-Parimarjana* (external therapies) and *Shastra-Pranidhana* (therapies requiring surgical intervention). *Pada Dhara* is included in *Bahi-Parimarjana* type of treatment. Based on mode of application, the *Bahya* procedures may be classified into

pouring type: medicated *Kvatha*, *Ksheera* or *Sneha* etc., are poured from a specific distance over the required places. It may be *Ekanga* like *Pada Dhara* or *Sarvanga* like *Kayaseka*. *Snehana* is the main *Purvakarma* (preparatory procedures) of *Panchakarma* (five bio-cleansing therapies). Literally *Snehana* means to oleate or to make smooth. *Acharya Charaka* has said that the procedure which causes unctuousness, fluidity, softness and moistness in the body is *Snehana* or Oleation therapy. The fatty substances used in this therapy are for the purpose of producing lubrication or oleating effect on the internal as well as external organs. This treatment has qualities like restfulness, strength, and invigoration and cognition³. Generally, *Sneha Dravya* are having properties like *Drava* (fluidity), *Sukshma* (minuteness), *Sara*

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(mobility), *Snigdha* (unctuousness), *Picchila* (sliminess), *Guru* (heaviness), *Sheeta* (coldness), *Manda* (slowness) and *Mridu* (softness) which are having antagonistic properties of *Rukshana* (dryness) *Dravya Swedana* is the process by which the sweat or perspiration is produced in the body by using various methods. *Swedana* is the procedure which relieves Stiffness, Heaviness and Coldness of the body and produces Sweating. It is the specific treatment for a number of disorders especially in Vata dominant diseases. The drugs used for *Swedana* therapy should possess following properties-*Ushna* (hotness, *Tejas Mahabhut Pradhana*), *Tikshna* (sharp- ness), *Sara* (mobility), *Snigdha* (unctuousness), *Ruksha* (dryness), *Sukshma* (minuteness), *Drava* (fluidity), *Sthira* (stability) and *Guru* (heaviness).⁴

2. Material and method

2.1. Materials Required

The following equipment should be made available for conduction of the procedure.

- *Droni or Dhara* table- This is a waist high table that is used to perform *Abhyanga* as well as the *Dhara* procedure. The upper surface is shallow and con- cave. An outlet is located at the foot of the table. The top end of the table has a separate rounded part and the surface of the table also forms a concave slight depression.
- 2 *Dharapatra* or *Sarawa* (of 2 litre capacity) (as in Figure 1 Below)
- 2 Vessels of 3 litres capacity (1 litre more than the *dharapatra* capacity)
- 2 Dry and clean towels.
- 2 litres of Medicated oil.
- 1 Helper to assist for changing the Medicated oil.
- Bowl of 150 ml capacity for *Taila* dispensing.
- Wide mouthed vessel for indirect heating of Medicated oil.
- Gas stove/induction heater
- Warm drinking water if required by the patient.
- Cold water for sprinkling if any complications are observed.

2.2. Procedure

Examination of patient: The patient is examined with reference to with *Dashvidha Pariksha* (Tenfold examination) and the *Vyadhi* (disease) as well as *Deha Bala* should be evaluated using *Pratyaksha* (direct perception), *Aptopadesha* (advice from the wise) and *Anumana* (inferential rea- soning). The affected area of feet should be examined properly for abrasions and injuries, then the tender area marked.

2.3. Preparation of the patient

The *Dhara Karma* is to be done in the morning hours after the evacuation of the bowel and bladder. The patient is made to lie down or to sit erect on the *Abhyanga* table. The affected feet is properly exposed. To begin with, the patient is subjected to local *Abhyanga* procedure. The limbs are supported in a horizontal position ensuring that the patient is also comfortable.

2.4. Main procedure

The bowl containing medicated oil is heated gently by keeping over hot water (water bath). The lukewarm *Taila* (having bearable warmth to the patient) is poured into the *Dhara* pot and made to flow on the feet-ankle joint in a regular, steady stream. The height of the stream should be maintained at 12 *Angula* (approx. 9 inches) throughout the procedure. Mild massage should be done with left hand continuously along with the flowing oil. The medicated oil should be continuously taken and reheated in order to maintain the temperature throughout the procedure. The medicated oil can be used for three days consecutively and fresh oil should be used on every fourth day of the procedure.

2.5. Signs of properly administered procedure

Samyak Lakshana of *PadaDhara* is not mentioned in classics. Since it is a type of *Swedana* and *Snehana*, *Samyak Swedana* and *Samyak Snehana Lakshana* can be considered. Among *Samyak Swedana Lakshana* *Sheetoparama*, *Stambhanigraha*, *Gauravanigraha* and *Vyadhihani* can be considered for assessment. In case of *Samyak Snigdha Lakshana* *Snigdha Gatratva* and *Mrdu Gatratva* can be taken for assessment.

2.6. Time duration

The medicated oil should be poured for ten thousand *Matra Kala*. Hence the procedure is performed for 40-50 minutes each day, for 7 days, 14 days or 21 days

2.7. Mode of Action of Pada dhara

The therapeutic action of *Pada Dhara* depends on: Procedural action of *Swedana* and the pharmacological action of the medicine. The actions of *Swedana* can be understood as *Stambhaghna*: *Swedana* relieves *Stambha* (stiffness) *Chimchimayan Stambha* is mainly caused by *Vyana Vayu, Sleshmaka Kapha, Amarasa, Mamsa, Meda* and *Vasa*. *Vayu* by *Rooksha Guna* absorbs *Snigdhatva* so causes *Stambha*. *Swedana* by its *Snigdha* and *Ushna Guna* does *Sroto- suddhi* (cleansing of micro channels) and *Amapachana*, thereby relieving stiffness.⁵

- *Gouravaghna*: It causes excretion of watery content (*Apya Ghataka*) of the body through *Swedana*. *Apya Tatva* is *Guru*. Due to elimination, lightness is achieved.
- *Sheetaghna*: *Swedana* is chiefly *Ushna* (hot) and thus relieves *Sheeta* (coldness) by opposite property.
- *Swedakaraktva*: *Swedana* promotes sweating. *Sweda* is a type of *Mala* and impurities come out through it from the body. *Swedana* drugs by *Ushna* and *Teekshna Guna* are capable of penetrating the microcirculatory channels (*Srotas*) where they activate the sweat gland to produce more sweat.
- The dilation of the microchannels allows *Laghu* and *Sara Guna* to act on *Dosha* in the channels, to remove stagnation, to make the sticky content mobile to excrete them into micro pores in the form of sweat.

2.8. The Pharmacological Action of the Medicine

Different drugs are used in various types of *Dhara Karma*. *Swedana* causes vasodilatation by which drugs enter into the body. According to Acharya Sushruta, each of the four *Tiryakdhamani* gradually divides up one hundred thousand times, making them countless. The body is connected to *Romakupa* as well as the network. *Veeryas* from *Abhyanga, Parisheka, Avagaha, Alepa* etc. enter the body through them after they have undergone *Paka* in the skin with *Bhrajaka Pitta*⁶

2.9. Ayurvedic Point of View

Swedana is *Stambhaghna, Gauravghna, Sheetaghna, Sweda Karakatva*. It can be explained as:

- *Stambhaghna*: *Stambha* is due to *Samana Vayu* which promotes *Agni, Shleshmaka Kapha, Amarasa, Mamsa, Meda, Vasa*. *Samana Vayu* due to its *Ruksha Guna*, absorbs *Snigdhatva* and also due to loss of function of *Sleshmaka Kapha* *Stambhana* occurs. *Swedana* is *Snigdha* and *Ushna*. *Ushna Guna* of *Swedana* does *Srotoshuddhi* and *Amapachana*, so it relieves *Stambha*.
- *Gauravghna*: Through *Sweda Apyaghataka*- liquid substances of the body come out of the body. As *Apyatatva* is *Guru* its expulsion from the body results in lightness. *Swedana* stimulates muscles and nerves and so lightness is gained.
- *Sheetaghna*: *Swedana* is mainly *Ushna* so it relieves *Sheeta* by opposite property⁷.
- *Sweda Karakatva*: *Sweda* is a type of *Mala*, impurities from the body comes out with *Sweda*.
- *Srotaha Su Abhiviliyate*: It helps to dissolve *Kapha* which is in a dense stage stuck to the channels firmly. Further, it liquifies *Kapha* allowing it to move freely.
- *Khani Mardavam Ayanti*: It makes the channels soften by this *Vata* flows in normal direction.
- *Sleshma Vishyandate*: It increases the secretions of vitiated *Kapha* through the channels *Swedana* drugs by its *Ushna* and *Tikshna Guna* are capable of penetrating the microcirculatory channels (*Srotasa*) where they activate the sweat glands to produce more sweat. Due to dilatation, *Laghu* and *Sara Guna* of these drugs enable them to act on *Snigdha Dosha* in the channels and direct them to move towards *Koshta* or excrete them through micropores of the skin in the form of sweat, resulting in *Sroto Shodhana*.⁹

2.10. Modern View

Swedana operates as the metabolism of body increases. *Swedana Ushna Guna* expands the capillaries and increases the circulation. Increasing circulation increases waste disposal and increased absorption of *Sneha* or drugs by the skin. It also promotes the rehabilitation of muscles and heat management may have the hypo analgesic effects.

2.10.1. Increased Metabolism

Tissue heating speeds up chemical changes, i.e. body temperature. Sympathetic activities are also increased because of the increased body temperature. Hormones such as epinephrine, nor-epinephrine, cortisol, thyroid hormones are released because of increased sympathetic activity, thus speeding up the metabolism rate. The increased metabolism means that oxygen and food products are being increasingly demanded and waste products, including metabolites, are being produced. Two important mechanisms for reducing heat are employed when the temperature of the body is too high in Swedana Karma.

2.10.2. Vasodilation

When body temperature increases, a negative feedback action is activated in order to achieve a normal temperature. Higher blood temperatures stimulate thermal receptors that transfer nerve impulses to the present area of the brain that stimulates the thermal center, in turn, and inhibits the heat fostering center. The heat losing center nerve impulses cause blood vessel dilation in the skin. So, radiation and conduction are used to lose excess heat to the environment. Due to vasodilatation, blood flow through the area increases to supply the necessary oxygen and nutrients and remove waste products.

2.10.3. Induction of Sweating

Figure 1 Sthanik taila Dhara

By hypothermic activation of sympathetic nerves, a high temperature of blood stimulates sweat glands of the skin, resulting in excessive sweating. Increased body temperature by one degree causes sufficient sweat to reduce the basic body heat production rate 10 times. Body temperature rises to over 2-3 degrees Celsius during Swedana Karma. The above-mentioned mechanism results in increased sweating. So, it can be inferred that the Ushna Guna of Swedana Karma leads to stimulation of sympathetic nervous system and there is vasodilation with increased sweating.¹⁰

3. Discussion

Is *Snehana and Swedana* in the form of *Janu Dhara*, and it is a very promising therapy to relieve the Symptoms *Dhara Karma* is one of the treatment mentioned under *Murdha Tail Chikitsa as Shirodhara*. The same *Dhara*, when applied on any localised part then it is called as *Ekanga Dhara* According to *Acharya Sushruta*, the *Veerya* of the *Dravyas* applied over the skin is absorbed by *Tryagaami Dhamanis*, which are present all over the body and are attached to *Romakoopas*. *Swedana* open these *Romakoopas*. These *Dravyas* are mostly *Ushna*, *Teekshna*, *Laghu*, in properties and thereby ascertain *Kaphvatahara* and *Shopahara* effects. Due to these properties oil reaches the target part. Hence these will be helpful in pacification of the vitiated *Vata Dosha*.

4. Conclusion

The main line of treatment as explain in samhita of *sandhigata vata* is “*sneha upanaha agnikarma bandhana unmardanani cha*” hence *snehana* in the form of *Pada dhara* is recommended in conditions like Peripheral Neuritis. It may help to increase blood circulation to the affected area gets rid of *Dosha* imbalances, strengthens the muscles in the area, helps the release of toxins and reduces inflammation. Due to the effect of medicated oils used, the procedure of *Pada Dhara* pacifies *Vata Dosha* and thus is especially effective in *Vata Vyadhi*, making it an easy yet effective treatment in disorders related to the Peripheral Nerves.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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